

The Basic Values of State Defense as a Defense in the Face of Threats, Challenges, Obstacles, and Disturbances

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ABSTRACT : State defense has a very close relationship to realizing the goals of the state as stated in the preamble to the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia in paragraph IV. State defense is an effort to defend the state through the determination, attitude, and spirit as well as the actions of all citizens in an organized and integrated manner which is inspired by the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia based on Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia to face all forms of challenges, threats, obstacles, and disturbances. , both coming from outside and from within, directly or indirectly, jeopardizes integrity in realizing the country's goals. The purpose of this paper is to find out the importance of inculcating the basic values of defending the country to realize national goals through the process of character building in the life of society, nation, and state.

KEYWORDS – State defense, threats, challenges, obstacles, disturbances.

I. INTRODUCTION

State defense is a constitutional obligation as an Indonesian citizen as well as an obligation as a human being as emphasized by Moh. Mahfud MD. Furthermore, Mahfud explained, as a citizen, you are required to have a sense of nationalism (nationalism) or a deep love for the homeland so that you must be ready to defend and sacrifice for its survival. Thus, there is a reciprocal achievement between the protection of the rights granted by the state and the willingness to sacrifice for the survival of the nation and state (Mahfud MD, 2009).

Awareness of defending the state is an important part of the national strategy of the Indonesian nation and state in dealing with various threats, disturbances, obstacles, and challenges. The history of the founding of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia (NKRI), which was obtained through a long and sacrificial struggle, cannot be separated from the roles and contributions of all components of the nation. The Indonesian state and nation must exert all their efforts to achieve the national goals as stated in the preamble of the 1945 Constitution, namely protecting the entire nation and the homeland of Indonesia, advancing public welfare, educating the nation life, and participating in carrying out world order. The Indonesian people work together to achieve this national goal to achieve the ideals of the Indonesian people, namely to create an independent, united, sovereign, just, and prosperous Indonesian state.

To achieve the national goals and ideals of the Indonesian people, a national strategy is needed to deal with the dynamics of the development of the strategic environment, both at the global, regional, and national levels. Every country needs to have a national strategy, considering that the dynamics of the development of the strategic environment can not only have a positive influence in the form of opportunities, but can also have a

negative effect in the form of threats, disturbances, obstacles, and challenges, or what is known as the nature of threats to the Indonesian state.

The national defense strategy that can guarantee the establishment of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia (NKRI), as well as respond to future national defense challenges, is the implementation of the Universal Defense System in the form of a Layered Defense Strategy that synergizes military defense with non-military defense. It is a manifestation of the participation of all Indonesian citizens in national defense efforts by making maximum use of all national resources. The basic thing about this universal national defense is the need for awareness to defend the country from all Indonesian citizens from all walks of life (WIRA Magazine, 2017).

II. Research and methods

This study uses a qualitative descriptive method. According to Arikunto (2013:3), Descriptive research is research conducted to investigate the circumstances, conditions, or other things that have been mentioned, and the results are presented in the form of a report study. Meanwhile, Moleong (2011:6) explains the meaning of qualitative research namely: Qualitative research is research that intends to understand the phenomenon of what is experienced by research subjects such as behavior, perception, motivation, action, and others holistically, and by way of description in the form of words and language, on special contexts that are natural and by utilizing various natural methods. By collecting secondary data in the form of electronic documents and physical documents both sourced from books, accredited journals, and applicable laws and regulations. Furthermore, the collected data is processed by summarizing and selecting things that are considered important and looking for themes and patterns to conclude.

III. Discussion

The essence of defending the country in national defense

Awareness of defending the state has been mandated in Article 27 paragraph (3) of the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia which reads: "Every citizen has the right and is obliged to participate in efforts to defend the state". Furthermore, Article 30 paragraph (1) of the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia, reads: "Every citizen has the right and is obliged to participate in the defense and security of the state". Further elaboration of state defense is contained in the Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 3 of 2002 concerning State Defense Article 9, which states that state defense is the attitude and behavior of citizens who are inspired by their love for the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia based on Pancasila and the Constitution (UUD) 1945 in ensuring the survival of the nation and state.

These attitudes and behaviors do not just appear to be the consciousness of every citizen from birth, so they need to be nurtured from an early age and always maintained and developed continuously through fostering awareness of defending the country.

The essence of fostering awareness of defending the state is an effort to build the character of the Indonesian nation which has the spirit of nationalism and patriotism and has strong national resilience to ensure the establishment of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia based on Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution and the maintenance of the implementation of national development in achieving national goals. Related to this fact, there are three basic questions about defending the country that needs to be answered to better understand the meaning of defending the country itself.

First, "What should be defended from the state?". Law Number 3 of 2002 concerning National Defense Article 4 states that national defense aims to maintain and protect the sovereignty of the state, the territorial integrity of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia, and the safety of the entire nation from all forms of threats. The article shows that what must be defended from the state is state sovereignty, territorial integrity, and national safety.

Second, "Why should the state be defended?". Each country has its own national interests which sometimes clash between one country and another. These conditions make the country need to survive given the

increasingly strong competition and no one can guarantee that a country will remain forever or remain to stand. For this reason, to survive, the state must be defended and protected from various forms of threats.

Third, "Who should defend the country?". The task of defending the country cannot only depend on the Indonesian National Army (TNI) alone. Like the universal defense system, defending the country must involve all components of the nation, including all citizens, state institutions, social institutions, to political parties (political superstructure and infrastructure).

The participation of Indonesian citizens in efforts to defend the state is a constitutional right and obligation of every citizen which is manifested in attitudes and behaviors that are imbued with love for the state in ensuring the survival of the nation and state. The fulfillment of these rights and obligations is aimed at establishing a national defense force to maintain state sovereignty, territorial integrity, and national safety.

Basic values of National Defense

Defending the country is not only the duty of the TNI and Polri, defending the country is also the duty and obligation of all of us as an embodiment of our love for Indonesia. The basic values of defending the country are love for the homeland, awareness of the nation and state, loyalty to Pancasila as the state ideology, being willing to sacrifice for the nation and state, and the initial ability to defend the country (Balitbang Hukum dan HAM, Kementrian Hukum dan HAM, 2021).

1. Love the Motherland

Love is a feeling (feel) that grows from the deepest heart of every citizen towards the homeland, namely the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia based on Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia, which include:

1. Knowledge of the history of the struggle for Indonesian independence
2. Natural resource potential
3. The potential of human resources, as well as
4. The geographical position is very strategic and famous for its natural beauty as the emerald of the equator which is a gift from God Almighty to the Indonesian people.

Understanding the existence of Indonesia as a whole, will foster the basic values of defending the country as a sense of pride as a warrior nation, a sense of belonging as the next generation, and a sense of responsibility as an expression of gratitude to God Almighty. With the growing sense of love for the homeland in every Indonesian citizen, a strong attitude toward defending the country will be born as the basic capital of the strength of the nation and state that is ready to sacrifice to protect, protect and build the nation and state towards the realization of national ideals.

2. National and State Awareness

The high sense of love for the country from every citizen needs to be supported by an attitude of national awareness that always creates the values of harmony, unity, and unity in diversity in their respective environments as well as an attitude of state awareness that upholds the basic principles of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia. as a legal state based on Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia. To foster an attitude of awareness of an independent and sovereign nation and state among other countries in the world, it is necessary to understand the values contained in the conception of nationality which include:

1. Archipelago Insight
2. National defense
3. National Precautions
4. And Free and Active Foreign Policy.

By understanding the concept of nationality adopted by the Indonesian people, it is hoped will give birth to an attitude of defending the country that upholds the values of national unity and national unity based on an attitude of nationalism and patriotism to strengthen national resilience with an archipelago perspective.

Strong, solid, and reliable national resilience is a great potential of the nation and state in anticipating and overcoming various forms of AGTH, both coming from within the country and from abroad as a form of national vigilance. With a conscious attitude toward defending the country, it will strengthen the unity and integrity of the nation as the main strength of the Indonesian nation in ensuring the integrity of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia throughout the ages.

3. Loyal to Pancasila as the State's Ideology

Pancasila as the ideology of the nation and state has proven effective in ensuring the survival of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia, which was proclaimed its independence on August 17, 1945. Since the Proclamation of Indonesian independence, historical events have occurred repeatedly that threaten the existence of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia, but various forms of these threats can be overcome, thanks to the loyalty of the Indonesian people to the Pancasila ideology. To build the loyalty of every citizen to the Pancasila ideology, it is necessary to understand the various factors that also influence the development of the experience of Pancasila values as part of the basic values of defending the country which include:

1. Enforcement of discipline
2. Development of political ethics, and
3. The democratic system, and
4. Fostering law-abiding.

The loyalty of every citizen to Pancasila as the state ideology and at the same time as the basis of the state, needs to be translated into the life of society, nation and state as a guarantee for the survival of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia based on Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia.

4. Willing to Sacrifice for the Nation and Country

The struggle of the Indonesian people to gain independence and maintain it until now is thanks to the determination of the nation's fighters who are willing to sacrifice for the sake of their nation and country. This attitude of self-sacrifice has become historical evidence that Indonesia's independence was obtained through a sincere, selfless struggle from all the people's forces against the Dutch colonial and anti-NKRI groups. With an unyielding spirit, the nation's fighters advanced to the battlefield, both military physical war and diplomatic war to achieve victory. To build an attitude of self-sacrifice for the nation and state, every citizen needs to understand several aspects which include:

1. The conception of the soul;
2. Fighting spirit and values 45;
3. ethical responsibilities;
4. Morals and constitution; as well as
5. The attitude of prioritizing national interests over personal or group interests.

With an attitude of being willing to sacrifice for the sake of the nation and state, one will be able to build the strength of the nation to build a strong, solid, and reliable national resilience and the success of national development rests on the potential of the nation and state independently.

5. Have Early National Defense Ability

The initial ability to defend the state of each citizen is defined as the potential and readiness to take action to defend the state by their profession and abilities in their respective environments or the public environment that requires the participation of state defense efforts. Every citizen has the initial ability to defend the country based on the basic values of defending the country from the aspect of self-ability such as self-confidence values, professional values, and so on in anticipating and overcoming various forms of threats, challenges, and obstacles, disturbances through various actions. from simple to large.

Every citizen has taken actions to defend the country in various aspects, namely: demographic aspects, geography, natural resources, the environment, ideology, politics, economy, socio-culture, technology, and

defense and security aspects. In connection with the very dynamic development of science and technology and globalization, it has resulted in the impact of various forms of threats, challenges, obstacles, increasingly complex and sophisticated disturbances that need the support of the attitude of every citizen to play a joint role in anticipating and overcoming them as a form of defending the country.

For the action to defend the state to be optimally successful, it is necessary to have a common understanding of the various forms of threats, challenges, obstacles, and disturbances, so that the action to defend the state becomes a more effective national movement. To understand the forms of threats, challenges, obstacles, disturbances in each environment, it is necessary to conduct a simple analysis, taking into account the existing potential, including local wisdom, and factual or potential threats, so that state defense action as a solution to each problem can develop from the perspective of the same one. Defending the country with the same understanding in anticipating and overcoming every form of threat, challenge, obstacle, the disturbance will become a national movement for defending the country that is very potential and efficient in optimally building national resilience and succeeding in national development (E-book *Bela Negara Bakesbangpol Provinsi Banten*, 2019).

Implementation of the basic values of the National Defense

The current era of globalization provides space for all Indonesian people to more easily recognize, and understand the ways of thinking and cultures of other nations. Understanding other cultures too deeply and ignoring your own can have dire consequences. The sense of love for one's nation disappears and pride in one's nation disappears. The Indonesian people have been dragged too far in globalization so that many forget their national identity and do not even know their own national identity. A sense of pride in what the nation has will erode the sense of nationalism. The spirit of Indonesian nationalism is getting less and less.

The fading of national character and identity as individuals and as Indonesian people has serious implications for the destruction or loss of the nation's character. The destruction of the nation's character will have a significant effect on national identity. And now the condition of the Indonesian nation has tended to damage the character of the nation's children. Anarchic actions, racial conflicts, and separatism are often crucial problems in this country because of the loss of the spirit of unity and integrity of the nation's children, the loss of the motto *Bhineka Tunggal Ika*, and the loss of the soul of love for the homeland. Therefore, from the various challenges faced by this nation, the discourse of defending the state has emerged as a long-term solution to answer these problems (Sri Indriyani Umra, 2019).

a. Defend the State Physically

According to Law no. 3 of 2002 concerning National Defense, the participation of citizens in the physical defense of the country can be done by becoming a member of the Indonesian National Army and becoming a reserve component. This idea is not meant to be an attempt to militarize civil society, but to introduce "civic dual function". This is meant as an effort to socialize the "concept of defending the state" in which the task of state defense and security is not solely the responsibility of the TNI, but is the rights and obligations of all citizens of the Republic of Indonesia.

b. Defend the State Non-Physically

State defense does not always have to mean "bearing arms against the enemy" or militaristic defense of the state. According to Law No. 3 of 2002, the participation of citizens in non-physical state defense can be carried out through civic education and service according to the profession. Citizenship education is given to instill the spirit of nationalism and love for the homeland. Civic education can be carried out through formal and non-formal channels. Based on this, the involvement of citizens in non-physical state defense can be carried out in various forms, at all times, and in all situations (Luh Suryatni, 2019), for example by:

1. Active, responsive, and alert to suspect and report related activities of a group of people related to terrorism, drug trafficking, and other actions that threaten state security.
2. Participate in civic education both through formal and non-formal channels.

3. Take an active role in participating in overcoming threats, especially non-military threats, for example flood disaster volunteers.
 1. Paying taxes and levies that function as a source of state financing to carry out development.
 2. Creating an atmosphere of calm and peace and harmony in the community.
 3. Appreciate the differences between fellow members of the community between race, ethnicity, religion, and also groups.
 4. Be selective and careful of foreign cultures (bkkp@bulelengkab.go.id, 2022).
 5. Implement the 3M health protocol and support the Covid-19 vaccination program.
 6. Use social media wisely by not spreading Hoax news and hate speech.

IV. Conclusion

Indeed, State Defense is instilled as a basic value in the life of the nation and state, this applies to all components of the nation regardless of religion, ethnicity, profession, or social status. In our observation, there is still a reluctance for some people to practice the values of State Defense because of the lack of understanding of the true meaning of State Defense. So far, State Defense has been associated with militarism and is a product of the new order, even though if we examine it further, State Defense has a meaning, which is very broad, even maintaining personal health is the simplest form of embodiment of the values of Defending the State, because only when we are healthy can we carry out activities by implementing the basic values of Defending the State in daily life. All components of the Nation are expected to become a strength and a defense against all forms of threats, challenges, obstacles, and disturbances.

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